

Soil type (World Reference Base) map of Europe based on Ensemble Machine Learning and multiscale EO data

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Important declarations

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Associated Data

Data supplied by the author:

Data are available from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838408>. The code is available from <https://github.com/AI4SoilHealth/>.

Required Statements

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The paper describes the production of a high spatial resolution (30 m) soil type map for the pan-EU based on the IUSS's World Reference Base classification system and Ensemble Machine Learning with a large set of covariates. 19,680 legacy soil survey points collated from multiple national and European projects were harmonized and combined to produce a consistent set of training points with a total of 185 classes. The training points were overlaid by 130 covariate layers containing climatic variables (CHELSA Bioclimatic variables), Landsat-based long-term (2000–2022) biophysical indices, multiscale terrain variables (at 30, 60, 120, 240, 480 and 960 m resolutions) and parent material variables. Predictions of soil-type probabilities were produced by fitting an ensemble model based on Random Forest and LightGBM. The results of the variable importance analysis indicate that the model is mainly driven by relief and climate factors. The accuracy assessment reveals a moderate decrease in the logarithmic loss of the model from 4.41 to 2.76 (about 37%) compared to the dummy model. Visually, the produced predictions match existing coarse resolution (1 km) pan-EU products, but then reveal significantly more detail, especially in areas with complex topography. The intended uses of the 30 m resolution maps include: (1) to help distinguish different soil regions (cross between soil types and climatic variables), (2) to assist in predictive soil mapping of soil properties with limited laboratory data, (3) to serve as a covariate in agronomy and forest species distribution models, e.g. to map yields and for species distribution mapping. The data and code used are publicly available under an open license from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838408> and <https://github.com/AI4SoilHealth/>.

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10 ABSTRACT

11 The paper describes the production of a high spatial resolution (30 m) soil type map for the pan-EU
12 based on the IUSS's World Reference Base classification system and Ensemble Machine Learning with
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29 INTRODUCTION

30 Soil types and soil classification are fundamental to a holistic understanding of soil ecosystems. Soil
31 classification and its application to soil mapping are based on pedogenic-landform relationships and
32 defined by relatively permanent soil properties formed by long-term soil genesis (Bouma et al., 2022).
33 Soil types and their delineation on maps are based on the concept of polypedons (distinct bodies of

34 relatively homogeneous material and homogeneous diagnostic soil-forming processes), which often
35 follow a topographic sequence called “*soil catena*” (Schaetzl and Anderson, 2005). Knowing the soil
36 types of Europe in high spatial detail is in the spotlight these days because soil types reflect vertical
37 soil stratification and diagnostic features/soil properties that can be used for a soil health assessment,
38 crop-yield modeling, land use planning, and landscape modeling of natural hazards. Detailed maps of soil
39 types can be used to support spatial planning and environmental policy (van Delden et al., 2011; Brungard
40 et al., 2015; Bouma et al., 2022; Rossiter et al., 2022); these soil data could eventually be adopted into
41 legislation and become the basis for the establishment of, for example, soil regions (Panagos et al., 2024).
42 Conventional soil type mapping methods are now seen as ineffective in producing detailed soil maps
43 cost-effectively and promptly (Kempen et al., 2012; Brevik et al., 2016). In contrast, soil scientists are
44 increasingly using ancillary data and machine learning to map soil properties and classes (Lamichhane
45 et al., 2019; Arrouays et al., 2020; Wadoux et al., 2020; van der Westhuizen et al., 2023). These ancillary
46 data, known as environmental covariates, can be sourced from digital elevation models (DEM), remote
47 sensing data, and gridded climatological data and are often the basis for improving the accuracy of soil
48 maps (Wadoux et al., 2020).

49 Over the last two decades, series of studies have been published in which legacy soil field observations
50 of soil types (points) are used to generate predictions of distribution of soil types or soil classes using some
51 of the common Machine Learning frameworks. Hengl et al. (2017) produced Random Forest-based global
52 predictions of probabilities for some 118 World Reference Base (WRB) soil types, but only at a relatively
53 coarse resolution of 250 m. Láng et al. (2016) tested a numerical approach to derive WRB Reference
54 Soil Groups (RSGs) by training the Random Forest (RF) model using no environmental covariates but
55 other soil properties measured in soil profiles. Duan et al. (2022) applied a standard ML workflow of a
56 tree-based algorithm on multispectral remote sensing data and texture features to map five types of soils
57 in Laoshan Country, China. Adding the soil texture to the list of covariates in their study resulted in an
58 increase in the accuracy of 12%. Calzolari et al. (2021) applied multiple linear regressions (MLR) and
59 general linear models (GLM) to predict the composition of map units in terms of 3 different (Leptosols,
60 Regosols and Cambisols) WRB RSGs in Sardinia. Camera et al. (2017) used ML to predict 30 soil
61 types (RSG and principal qualifier) in Cyprus; Heung et al. (2016) mapped 16 Soil Taxonomy great
62 groups in the Lower Fraser Valley, British Columbia, Canada; Taghizadeh-Mehrjardi et al. (2015) mapped
63 taxonomic distance of 5 Soil Taxonomy families in Baneh Region, Iran; Stum et al. (2010) used Random
64 Forest to map 24 soil classes in Utah, USA; Brungard et al. (2015) mapped 30 Soil Taxonomy subgroups
65 in three states (New Mexico, Utah and Wyoming) also using Random Forest; Žižala et al. (2022) mapped
66 WRB RSG’s in Czechia; Pásztor et al. (2018) used object-based and multi stage classification method
67 to create a new Hungarian Soil Type map containing 40 soil types in Hungarian classification; Dornik
68 et al. (2018) classified 10 WRB RSG’s in 3 administrative territories of Romania using Geographic object
69 based image analysis. Overall, this short literature review shows that tree-based algorithms are preferred
70 for soil type mapping when using continuous variables representing topography, climate, vegetation or
71 land use from remote sensing products, categorical variables representing parent material and legacy
72 maps. However, it is also worth noting that most applications of ML for soil mapping today focus
73 on mapping continuous soil properties: various physical and geochemical soil properties, pH, nutrient,

74 and micro-nutrient concentrations and similar. Significantly fewer studies (national, regional or global)
75 focus on mapping categorical soil variables, particularly soil taxonomic units i.e. soil types or parent
76 material classes (Giraldo et al., 2009; Heung et al., 2014). It almost appears that soil-type mapping is a
77 slowly disappearing field of pedometrics despite the major role of soil classification when defining soil
78 functionality (Bouma et al., 2022).

79 With the emergence of open Earth Observation (EO) data such as NASA's Landsat mission and
80 Copernicus Sentinel-2 mission, Copernicus DEM (Bielski et al., 2024) and similar high resolution data
81 sets, open analysis-ready covariate layers are now available for the entire land mask at 30 m spatial
82 resolution (Potapov et al., 2020). This means that producing high-resolution soil-type maps using machine
83 learning algorithms on the continental or global scale is now also possible. To our knowledge, there are
84 no examples of high-resolution WRB soil type maps for the European continent that cover all major soil
85 types in Europe. Legacy soil type maps for Europe include, for example, the Harmonized World Soil
86 Database 2.0 (HWSD 2.0) (Nachtergaele et al., 2023) and European Soil Database v2 Raster Library
87 1 km×1 km (ESDB v2) (Panagos et al., 2022); both are based on assigning dominant soil types to manually
88 digitized soil polypedons (distinct bodies of relatively homogeneous material and homogeneous diagnostic
89 soil-forming processes). Both HWSD 2.0 and ESDB v2 have a relatively coarse resolution (1 km) and
90 also lack thematic detail: the targeted classes consisting only of a principal qualifier (PQ) and RSG only.
91 It can be said that, in general, the spatial resolution of the European Soil Database v2 and its legend
92 (Pásztor et al., 2018) is not suitable for detailed spatial planning including at the farm scale, so its use is
93 often limited to providing overviews. Several member states of the European Union (EU) now put effort
94 in producing high resolution (30 m) national maps, but then this is unfortunately done using their (local)
95 national classification systems (Žižala et al., 2022; Pásztor et al., 2018). This does not help in producing
96 EU-wide soil data, as differences between national soil classifications are significant (Brevik et al., 2016)
97 and a simple merge is not trivial, although several correlation tables have been published and could be
98 used for this purpose (Krasilnikov et al., 2009).

99 In this paper, we describe a Soil Health Data Cube approach for mapping soil types at 30 m resolution
100 based on the WRB 2022 classification system. We use possibly the largest compilation of legacy point
101 data collated and imported within the [AI4SoilHealth](#) project. We then overlay these versus large stack of
102 high-resolution covariates, fit models, and generate predictions of probabilities per class. We implemented
103 several improvements compared to previous studies. Firstly, we extend the main resources for training
104 data with a number of new national legacy soil profiles of the member states. We also extended the
105 original list of training points and added secondary (expert-based) “soft” data which are points extracted
106 from ESDB v2 (we keep it to the maximum 5% of points from the overall set). This gave us a more
107 comprehensive European dataset of training soil points so that no geographic regions will be under-
108 represented. This harmonization resulted in a total of 185 WRB Soil Types in the training data set that
109 comprised 22,452 soil points. Secondly, we extend the list of covariate layers representing SCORPAN
110 soil forming factors (McBratney et al., 2003) also to a number of newly published (Earth Observation)
111 EO-based covariates (Tian et al., 2024a). Moreover, we apply an adjusted version of the multi-scale
112 approach proposed by Behrens et al. (2018) to the Digital Terrain Model (relief) covariates. This resulted
113 in significantly higher spatial detail of predictions (30 m), which is now much closer to matching the

114 catena concept. Thirdly, we predicted per-pixel probabilities of the Soil Types based on ensemble machine
115 learning models instead of only predicting the hard classes.

116 MATERIALS AND METHODS

117 The predictive mapping framework

118 In principle, there are (at least) three groups of methods to predict soil types per pixel i.e. to produce
119 complete consistent maps of the distribution of soil types:

- 120 1. **Rule-based systems:** Map diagnostic properties per pixel, then classify using classification rules.
- 121 2. **Machine-learning (fully agnostic) systems:** Directly map classes at lowest level, then aggregate
122 based on hierarchical rules.
- 123 3. **Hybrid mapping systems:** e.g. map first highest level groups (e.g. WRB RSG's), then map lower
124 level diagnostic horizons and diagnostic properties, then aggregate using decision rules.

125 In this work, we use a Machine Learning-based predictive mapping framework developed at Open-
126 GeoHub and which we refer to as “*EO-soilmapper*”. Here “*EO*” stands for Earth Observation (Fig. 1),
127 which emphasizes that most of the data used for mapping come from (ESA/NASA's) Earth Observation
128 missions, e.g. Copernicus GLODEM and Landsat 5/7/8 missions.

129 The three main advantages of the EO-soilmapper are: (1) it is a fully automated system, (2) it is
130 cost-effective as it uses publicly available EO data products and optimizes computing, (3) it uses variable
131 quality flags in training, i.e. it assigns weights proportionally to the quality of training data. Further
132 advantages and disadvantages of the EO-soilmapper approach are discussed in the Discussion section.

133 World Reference Base

134 The World Reference Base (WRB) for soil resources was started in 1998 at the World Congress of Soil
135 Science. Since then, it has had four editions, the last one being the 2022 edition (IUSS, 2022), which is
136 also used in this work. We also recommend using the illustrated version of WRB for practical purposes,
137 as photographs can be compared with what you observe in the field (Świtoniak et al., 2022).

138 The WRB is based on diagnostic horizons, diagnostic properties, and diagnostic materials, altogether
139 called diagnostics; assuming these are all determined accurately, a surveyor should be able to classify (by
140 opening at least 1 m deep profile or mini-profile) a site to one of the 32 Reference Soil Groups (RSGs)
141 and then add any responding principal qualifiers and/or supplementary qualifiers. WRB, although much
142 shorter / much less complex than USDA's Keys to Soil Taxonomy, carries a lot of critical information
143 about the soil site (see Fig. 2). On the other hand, mapping only WRB RSG's carries only limited amount
144 of detail as the difference between two types of more generic soil RSG's such as Cambisols, Luvisols,
145 Umbrisols and Phaeozems can be significant. Some authors have compared USDA Soil Taxonomy (ST)
146 and WRB and concluded that WRB is, for example, more suited to classify and separate the two paddy
147 soils, as it more precisely represented the state of water saturation by soil depths than the ST system (Lee
148 et al., 2023).

149 Some of the most common examples of practical uses of WRB include the following:

Figure 1. General seven-step framework for generating predictions as a part of the Soil Health Data Cube (AI4SoilHealth project). This is implemented as an automated workflow, allowing predictions to be updated and improved as new legacy soil data are harmonized and added to the training pool. Abbreviations: AW3D30 — ALOS World 3D 30 m Digital Surface Model (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, 2021), GLO30 — Copernicus GLO-30 Digital Surface Model (European Space Agency, 2024), NIR — Near Infrared, SWIR — Short-wave infrared, NDVI — Landsat Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, NDTI — Normalized Difference Tillage Index, MODIS — The NASA’s Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer, NUTS3 — EU’s small regions based on the NUTS (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics) classification, LST — land surface temperature, MODIS.

Mollic Gleysols
(Epiloamic, Katoarenic, Aric, Mulmic)

1–Gleysoil: has a layer, ≥ 25 cm thick and starting ≤ 40 cm from the mineral soil surface, that has gleyic properties throughout; and reducing conditions in some parts of every sublayer – in this case it starts at the mineral soil surface.

2–Mollic: mollic horizon - thick, very dark ($\geq 0.6\%$ soil organic carbon) humus horizon with well developed structure and high base saturation expressed by relatively high pH values.

3–Epiloamic: loamy (loam, sandy loam, clay loam, sandy clay loam or silty clay loam) material with thickness of ≥ 30 cm with lower limit ≤ 50 cm of the mineral soil surface.

4–Katoarenic: sandy (sand, loamy sand) material starts >0 and <50 cm from the (mineral) soil surface and has its lower limit ≥ 100 cm of the (mineral) soil surface.

5–Mulmic: very dark mineral material with $\geq 8\%$ soil organic carbon developed from organic material as a result of its fast decomposition after drainage.

Fluvic Calcaric Gleysols

2–Fluvic: fluvic material, ≥ 25 cm thick and starting ≤ 75 cm from the mineral soil surface. Fluvatile origin of sediment is recognized by distinct stratification in $\geq 25\%$ of its volume.

3–Calcaric: $\geq 2\%$ calcium carbonate equivalent. The carbonates are at least partially primary (inherited from the parent material).

Seasonally waterlogged soils affected by a shallow fluctuating groundwater table. They are developed mainly within or over permeable material and have prominently mottled or greyish coloured horizons within 40 cm depth. Most occupy low-lying or depressional sites.

Figure 2. Examples of WRB soil types (two types of Gleysols) with photographs (left), layer designation (center) and diagnostic properties and diagnostic horizons (right). This illustrates that soil types carry high density of information on both soil properties (e.g. soil organic matter content, soil texture, pH), soil forming conditions (e.g. stagnation of the water table), position in the landscape and similar. Image source: Świtoniak et al. (2022) and Land Information System (LandIS) AGNEY (A) soil series from <https://www.landis.org.uk/soilsguide/>.

- 150 • For correlating national systems for the purpose of data merging.
- 151 • For building legends for soil mapping units and/or soil districts: the most homogeneous landscape
- 152 units to simplify soil management strategies.
- 153 • For summarizing key soil forming processes and ecological conditions at meso-location (e.g.
- 154 landscape position, soil layer at some depth).
- 155 • For summarizing sequence of soil layers i.e. the vertical distribution of layers.
- 156 • For describing typical soil property distributions (see e.g. Beaudette et al. (2013)).

157 Some limitations of the WRB classification systems are:

- 158 • Number of soil types is theoretically speaking infinite as one can always produce different combi-
- 159 nation of RSG's and diagnostic properties and horizons. This creates practical problems as it is
- 160 difficult to generate a standard legend.
- 161 • WRB has in principle only 2–3 levels, making it relatively simple system, unlike ST which comes
- 162 with 6–7 levels.

- 163 • Various versions of WRB system is typically not harmonized, i.e. you need to develop own rules to
164 convert soil observations between different versions.
- 165 • WRB is still heavily under-used system with most of European countries using the national soil
166 type systems, while globally ST seems to be more mentioned in the literature.

167 It is also worth mentioning that some older FAO documentation on WRB is available only under
168 the NC-ND license, e.g. [Food and of the United Nations \(2006\)](#), while almost all ST documentation is
169 available as open materials, making them much less restrictive for general use.

170 **Training points: harmonization, quality control and binding**

171 To collate the most comprehensive pan-EU training dataset, we imported and merged all available
172 international, national and regional datasets from project partners (marked partner), national institutions
173 (marked institute) and publicly available datasets (Table 1). OpenGeoHub has signed a data protection
174 agreement in the case of about 70% datasets, therefore these point data are unfortunately not available in
175 the public domain.

Table 1. Overview of input datasets used for modeling pan-EU distribution of WRB soil types. Abbreviations: SOTER — Soil and Terrain Databases, WoSIS — World Soil Information Service, ESDB v2 — European Soil Database v2 Raster Library 1 km×1 km, FAO — Food and Agriculture Organization, WRB — World Reference Base.

Country	Source	System	N of points	Correlations to WRB 2022
Denmark	partner	FAO1974	1214	Batjes (2015) ; Nachtergaele et al. (2023)
Germany	Poeplau et al. (2020)	German	2861	Krasilnikov et al. (2009)
Belgium	Aardewerk-2010 (2011)	Belgian	933	Dondeyne et al. (2014)
Netherlands	PDOK (2020)	Dutch	2061	Krasilnikov et al. (2009)
Slovenia	institute	Slovenian	1800	Vrščaj et al. (2017)
Croatia	http://hrsoil.multione.hr/	Croatian	2055	Bašić (2013)
Portugal	Ramos et al. (2017)	WRB various	2889	IUSS (2022)
Italy	partner	WRB 2015	2576	IUSS (2022)
GeoCradle	GeoCradle (2021)	WRB various	300	IUSS (2022)
Hungary	partner	WRB 2015	65	IUSS (2022)
Estonia	institute	WRB 2015	123	IUSS (2022)
SOTER	Batjes (2005)	FAO 1990	662	Nachtergaele et al. (2023)
WoSIS	Batjes et al. (2017, 2024)	WRB 2015, FAO	1205	IUSS (2022) ; Nachtergaele et al. (2023)
ESDB v2	Panagos et al. (2022)	WRB various	1000	IUSS (2022)

176 Three types of soil profiles were presented in the training data set:

- 177 1. **The soil profiles in older WRB classifications:** These points were converted to the WRB 2022
178 with no semantic changes. The principal qualifiers were moved to the supplementary qualifiers and
179 vice versa. Because the majority of the points (85%) contained only one principal qualifiers, the
180 additional principal and supplementary qualifiers were excluded from the final legend. The only

181 exception was the Haplic principal qualifier for which the most important supplementary qualifier
182 was preserved. The points were assigned to quality codes 6 or 5 (Table 2).

183 2. **The soil profiles in national or FAO classifications:** These points were correlated to WRB using
184 already published conversion tables with forwarding corrections to the WRB 2022. The references
185 are provided in Table 1. The points were assigned to quality codes 4 or 3.

186 3. **The soil profiles have only WRB RSG assignments:** These points (15% of total points) were
187 assigned with the two most frequent principal qualifiers for the specific RSG. Therefore two
188 alternatives for the points were used in the training step. The points were assigned to quality codes
189 2 or 1.

Table 2. Weights for Machine Learning reflecting the quality of the training soil profiles based on the assigned quality class. Abbreviations: WRB — World Reference Base, FAO — Food and Agriculture Organization, RSG — Reference Soil Group, WoSIS — World Soil Information Service (Batjes et al., 2017, 2024), HWSD 2.0 — Harmonized World Soil Database 2.0. (Nachtergaele et al., 2023)

Weight	Code	Quality class
1	6	Original or simplified original WRB classification used (no semantic changes)
0.9	5	Older WRB classification converted to WRB 2022 (no semantic changes), i. e. principal qualifiers moved to supplementary qualifiers
0.8	4	National classification converted to WRB 2022 principal qualifiers and RSG using already published national conversion tables
0.6	3	National or FAO classification converted to WRB 2022 principal qualifiers and RSG using already published literature (see Table 1)
0.4	2	National classification to WRB 2022 using already published conversion tables for RSG, most frequent primary classifier added based on the other national resources
0.1	1	National classification to WRB 2022 using already published conversion for RSG, most frequent primary classifier of WoSIS/HWSD 2.0 for the Europe

190 The weights were used to penalize for some training points being of lower quality. We admit that
191 the conversion table we prepared is somewhat subjective, and we have made them publicly available for
192 comments and adjustments (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838408>). We used only WoSIS
193 points having the complete WRB classification and not only WRB RSG's. Some regions of Europe
194 (Spain, France, and Scandinavia) were underrepresented in the original training data set. Therefore, we
195 randomly sampled 1000 points from the WRB Full Legend layer of ESDB v2. Thus, these were not real
196 observations, but should be considered “pseudo-training points”. We also had to trim-down some data
197 sets as otherwise they would have introduced misbalance in the training. For example, we have selected
198 a representative sample (2061) from the original 200,000 Dutch profiles (or 1% of the original data)
199 using doubly-balanced sampling, creating a stratified sample in the geographical and thematic domain
200 (Grafström and Tillé, 2013).

201 Data harmonization resulted in 19,680 unique points. Harmonization resulted in 363 soil-type classes
202 consisting of the main principal qualifier and RSG. The total number of harmonized points used was
203 23,200, because for points with known RSG only, two of the most possible principal qualifiers were

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of all available training points (about 23,000 points shown on the map) with soil types. Highest quality national data are highlighted in green. Secondary ESDB v2 points extracted from the map are highlighted in brown. For data sources see Table 1.

204 added based on national records or the WoSIS database. Rows containing more than one soil type were
 205 duplicated using the same vector of covariates but the different target soil type. For modeling, we used
 206 soil type classes that have at least 6 points, which is a common standard in statistics (James et al., 2013).
 207 It resulted in 22,452 training points and 185 classes. The distribution of the points in Europe is shown in
 208 Fig. 3.

209 Covariates

210 We used various feature layers (Covariates) representing SCORPAN soil forming factors (McBratney et al.,
 211 2003) for predictive modeling. We focused especially long-term effects of soil, climate, relief, parent
 212 material as the long-term and the organisms (vegetation and human). The soil factor was represented by
 213 the normalized mean radar backscatter coefficients of the Sentinel-1 Global Backscatter Model (S1GBM)
 214 in 30 m spatial resolution, which is derived from SAR images captured during the 2016-2017 period.
 215 This model has been corrected for variations in incidence angles, ensuring global consistency (Bauer-
 216 Marschallinger et al., 2021). Radar backscatter is related, among others, to soil moisture (Celik et al., 2022)
 217 and soil type (Deodoro et al., 2023).

218 We represent the “organisms” factor of soil formation with spectral indices that represent various
 219 environmental factors, including vegetation, soil, crops, and water. We used long-term layers from the
 220 Landsat-based spectral index predictor data cube, as detailed in (Tian et al., 2024a). The long-term layers
 221 were calculated as P25, P50, and P75 percentiles of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI),

222 Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation
223 (FAPAR), and Bare Soil Fraction (BSF) derived for the years 2000-2022. These layers were available in
224 the 30 m spatial resolution from Zenodo.

225 Long-term climate features including annual patterns (e.g., average annual temperature, total annual
226 precipitation), seasonal variations (e.g., fluctuations in temperature and precipitation), and critical envi-
227 ronmental extremes (e.g., highest and lowest monthly temperatures, precipitation during the wettest and
228 driest quarters) were represented by the CHELSA BIOCLIM variables (Karger et al., 2017; Brun et al.,
229 2022b). All data layers were resampled to a 30-meter resolution, using cubic splines (using GDAL where
230 necessary), to maintain a uniform spatial extent, resolution and coordinate reference system throughout.

231 The relief covariates were generated from the Ensemble Global Digital Terrain Model (EDTM)
232 at a 30 m spatial resolution (Ho et al., 2024a). These variables included key terrain metrics such
233 as slope in degree, minimum and maximum curvature, hillshade, as well as negative and positive
234 openness. Hydrological parameters, such as the specific catchment area, slope length and steepness
235 (LS) factor, flow accumulation, and topographic wetness index (TWI), were derived using SAGA GIS.
236 Furthermore, landscape orientation and geomorphological features, including northernness, easternness,
237 and geomorphon classes, were calculated using GRASS GIS, which are essential for understanding
238 pedogenetic processes (Sena et al., 2020). Moreover, we calculated the so-called extended Gaussian
239 pyramids (GP) first proposed by Behrens et al. (2018). For large-scale, continental analyses, coarse-
240 resolution layers (240 m, 480 m, and 960 m resolution) we generated both terrain and hydrological
241 features from the pan-EU mosaics, while for fine-resolution layers (30 m, 60 m, and 120 m) were divided
242 DTM into tiles, padded with 3,400 pixels for geomorphon and hydrological Fig. 4 parameters, and 100
243 pixels for the other variables (Ho et al., 2024b). The DTM variables were calculated using the Equi7 grid
244 system to minimize data oversampling and preserve geometric accuracy (Bauer-Marschallinger et al.,
245 2014). The parent material was represented by the Continental Europe surface lithology map at 1:1M
246 scale (Isik et al., 2024).

247 **Cross-validation and feature selection design**

248 We followed the AI4SoilHelth prediction workflow described in Tian et al. (2024b) with modifications
249 to the classification of the imbalanced dataset. We divided the input data set into calibration (20% of
250 the points) and training (80% of the points) datasets. The calibration data set was used to tune the
251 hyperparameters of the machine learning models and the training data set was used to estimate the
252 accuracy of the models. Both data sets featured 5-fold spatial cross-validation to deal with clustered
253 data (De Bruin et al., 2022): either to select the best set of hyperparameters or to assess the accuracy of
254 the models. For CV, only primary points were used, i.e. excluding 1000 of extracted soil profiles from
255 ESDB v2, for the selection and evaluation of the accuracy of the best model. The weights from (Table 2)
256 were also used consistently to account for variable data quality.

257 To run the selection, we wrote our own code of 5-fold cross validation iterating over the newly added
258 block column because the original function GroupedKFold from scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011) was
259 unable to split the datasets into 5-folds using spatial blocks as grouping factor. First, we excluded all
260 classes that had less than 25 points, because we wanted to split the input data set into calibration (20%

Figure 4. Illustration of the effect of “scale” in predictive soil mapping: Topographic Wetness Index (TWI) for an area around Bucharest, Romania, Danube River Basin, derived using three spatial resolutions. A: 60 m DTM, B: 240 m DTM, C: 960 m DTM.

261 = 5 points) and training set (80% = 20 points) block-wise. Then, we assigned the membership of the
 262 input points to 10 km blocks and we excluded all classes that appeared in 4 or less blocks. Therefore, we
 263 made sure that each soil type could be split block-wise into five folds containing at least one spatial block
 264 with one observation. Second, we randomly selected 20% points in every class to form the calibration
 265 dataset. Third, a fold index was assigned to all calibration points falling in one block inside the each
 266 class. The fold index (0 to 4) was assigned repetitively block by block in each class, The fold indices
 267 were shuffled in each class and assigned as a new column to the calibration dataset. The fold column
 268 was then used in all cross-validation procedures to form the splits. This method prevented measurements
 269 from the same tiles from being included in both the training and testing folds simultaneously, ensuring
 270 a robust assessment of the models’ generalization capabilities across diverse geographic areas same as
 271 proposed by Roberts et al. (2017). The same procedure was applied on the training dataset resulting in
 272 two non-overlapping datasets of the same 110 unique soil types for benchmarking the models.

273 For feature selection we used the model-driven Repeated Subsampling-Based Cumulative Feature
 274 Importance (RSCFI) selection (Behrens et al., 2010; Jović et al., 2015; Wadoux et al., 2020). For this,
 275 we use the default RF model in *scikit-learn* as the initial algorithm. For the classification task, the
 276 method fitted models to the candidate features and selected the candidates based on mean decrease in
 277 impurity (Kawakubo and Yoshida, 2012; Han et al., 2016). This model was trained 50 times to enhance
 278 the robustness that is a cost-effective approach to permutation importance (Li et al., 2019), each time
 279 using the full set of candidate characteristics on different subsets of the calibration dataset selected via
 280 bootstrapping. In each iteration, 80% of the calibration data was randomly selected by spatial blocking,
 281 which involved choosing soil points from different tiles. Then the mean feature importance was calculated
 282 and all features below the mean threshold were discarded from the list of candidate features in each
 283 iteration. The final list of features was formed from features that appeared at least 25 times out of 50
 284 iterations. The resulting list of features was applied to the filter calibration and validation dataset before

285 hyperparameter tuning.

286 **Benchmarking of prediction models**

287 We tested two state-of-the-art machine learning models LightGBM (Ke et al., 2017) and RF as implemen-
288 tation in scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011). After some initial testing, these algorithms showed the best
289 performance with this data, which is also reported in other similar studies (Hengl et al., 2017; Lu et al.,
290 2023). Both RF and LightGBM were trained to return probabilities of occurrence of the soil types for
291 each pixel.

292 For each machine learning model, we set specific initial parameter space (see Table 3 and Table 4).
293 We used Optuna framework implemented in python to find the best set of the hyperparameters (Akiba
294 et al., 2019). The framework was used to identify the optimal hyperparameters using 50 trials. We also
295 implemented early stopping after 10 rounds of stagnating of the optimization criterion to LightGBM
296 model to prevent overfitting. Table 3 and Table 4 show also the final set of features selected by the Optuna
297 algorithm. In the case of LightGBM, the final *number of rounds* was also optimized by the framework.

Table 3. Hyperparameter space for the LightGBM classification model. The table shows also the final set of features selected by the optuna algorithm.

Hyperparameter	Feature Space	Final set
num_leaves {int}	[20,150]	44
max_depth {int}	[3,15]	10
learning_rate {float}	[0.001,0.1]	0.016
min_data_in_leaf {int}	[20,100]	96
feature_fraction {float}	[0.5,1]	0.812
bagging_fraction {float}	[0.5,1]	0.900
bagging_frequency {int}	[1,10]	8
lambda_l1 {float}	[0,10]	0.447
lambda_l2 {float}	[0,10]	6.323
min_gain_to_split {float}	[0,10]	0.393
num_boost_round {int}	[1, 500]	348

Table 4. Hyperparameter space for the RF regression model. The table shows also the final set of features selected by the optuna algorithm.

Hyperparameter	Feature Space	Final set
n_estimators {int}	[20,150]	138
criterion	{gini, entropy, log_loss}	gini
max_depth {int}	[2, 32]	9
max_features	{log2, sqrt}	log2
min_samples_split {int}	[2, 20]	3
min_samples_leaf {int}	[1, 20]	6

298 The optimisation metric of the hyperparameter tuning was minimizing the overall multiclass logistic
299 (log) loss metric using the 5-fold spatial cross-validation of the calibraton set (Bishop and Nasrabadi,

300 2006):

$$L_{log}(Y, P) = -\log Pr(Y|P) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} y_{i,k} \log p_{i,k}$$

301 where true labels are one-hot encoded binary indicator matrix Y and P is a matrix of probability estimates,
302 with $p_{i,k} = Pr(p_{i,k} = 1)$.

303 Once the models' hyperparameters were established, the two models were evaluated to select the best
304 candidate for map production. This evaluation was performed using 5-fold spatial cross-validation on the
305 training dataset. The overall multiclass log losses were compared to a dummy model that always returned
306 the empirical class prior distribution of the training set using the same workflow. We also derived a log
307 loss ratio as follows (Witjes et al., 2022):

$$R(Y, P) = 1 - \frac{L_{log}(Y, P)}{B_{log}(Y, P)}$$

308 where L_{log} is the overall log loss score of the model and B_{log} is the overall log loss score of the dummy
309 model. A ratio of 0 indicates that the model performed no better than a random predictor, while a ratio of
310 1 signifies perfect predictions, with a log loss score of 0.

311 To better understand the differences between the LightGBM and RF models, we also derived log loss
312 scores and log loss ratios and F1 scores for the top 25% of the most frequent soil types in the dataset from
313 the 5-folds of the block CV. Class-wise log loss scores were calculated using the formula (Bishop and
314 Nasrabadi, 2006):

$$L_{log}(y, p) = -\log Pr(y|p) = -(y \log(p) + (1-y) \log(1-p))$$

315 where Y is a binary matrix representing the expected class labels, N is the total number of observations, K
316 is the number of classes, P is the matrix of probabilities predicted by the model, $y_{i,k}$ indicates whether
317 sample i belongs to class k , and $p_{i,k}$ represents the probability that sample i belongs to class k .

318 To support the reader's understanding and allow comparison with other studies, we also calculated the
319 weighted F1 score (Van Rijsbergen, 1977):

$$WF_1 = \sum_{c=1}^n S_c \frac{2P_c R_c}{P_c + R_c}$$

320 where n represents the number of classes, while S_c denotes the support (i.e., the number of training points),
321 P_c is the precision (producer's accuracy), and R_c is the recall (user's accuracy) for a given class c .

322 We trained new instances of the models featuring the best set of hyperparameters merging the
323 calibration and validation set and performing classic stratified 5-fold cross-validation `StratifiedKFold`
324 from `scikit-learn` to get an estimate of the overall performance in all classes including extraordinary soil
325 types containing less than 25 points. The final model was selected by comparing overall log loss and F1
326 scores of LightGBM and RF models trained on 110 soil types and the models trained on all soil types and
327 the log loss ratios of the the top 25% of the most frequent soil types.

328 **Training final model an prediction**

329 The final model was trained using all available soil type data points, including points extracted from soil
330 maps. We applied weights to the training samples and selected only the most relevant features based on
331 their importance in previous model iterations. Since both the LightGBM and Random Forest models
332 achieved similar performance (as discussed in the Results section), we opted to ensemble their predictions.
333 The ensemble method averaged the predicted probabilities of each soil type for each pixel. This reduced
334 the risk of individual model bias while maintaining the accuracy of soil type classification across tiles.

335 For each tile, the prediction process began by loading the relevant input features (GIS layers). These
336 features included various environmental covariates, land use, and topography. They were retrieved from
337 a cloud-based data catalog. The LightGBM and Random Forest models were applied independently to
338 generate predictions. Both models produced probability distributions for all 185 soil types, each providing
339 its own assessment of the probable classifications. After generating these separate predictions, the results
340 from the two models were combined by a simple averaging of the probabilities.

341 The ensemble predictions were then saved in two distinct formats. First, a hard classification was
342 produced, representing the most probable soil type for each pixel. In addition, the ensemble probabilities
343 for each soil type were saved as individual layers. All output files were stored as Cloud-Optimized
344 GeoTIFFs (COG) and uploaded to cloud storage for inspection. After predicting soil types for all tiles,
345 the outputs were mosaicked into pan-European maps and uploaded to Zenodo. Permanent water bodies
346 and buildings were masked using the Pan-European land mask and the World Settlement Footprint 2019
347 datasets (DLR Geoservice of the Earth Observation Center, 2019).

348 **Visual assessment and uncertainty estimation**

349 The final predicted soil type probability maps and the hard class map were visually compared and assessed
350 to the ESDB v2 (WRBFU map) (Panagos et al., 2022). Moreover, we compared the soil type patterns of
351 the hard class map to the locations of the legacy data from the Systematic Soil Survey (SSS) database,
352 conducted from 1961 to 1970 as a conventional soil survey in the territory of former Czechoslovakia
353 (Žížala et al., 2022). The SSS database represents one of the most comprehensive national sources in
354 Europe, contains about 300,000 soil profiles. The SSS points were not used during the training, because
355 the legend contained only WRB 2022 RSGs. No more independent validation points were available.

356 To quantify uncertainty, we computed the relative entropy (the so-called “*Kullback-Leibler diver-*
357 *gence*”) (Kullback and Leibler, 1951) between the predicted probability distribution (p_k) and the uniform
358 distribution ($q_k = \frac{1}{N}$), where k is a soil type class and N is the number of classes. We used the uniform
359 distribution for q_k to represent the maximum uncertainty scenario, when each soil type is equally probable.
360 Relative entropy quantifies the expected “excess surprise” or additional information when the distribution
361 p_k is compared to q_k (Shannon, 1948). This approach allows us to assess, for each pixel, how much the
362 prediction of the model improves in a scenario of maximal uncertainty.

363 The relative entropy, $D_{KL}(p_k||q_k)$, is a non-negative function calculated as

$$D_{KL}(p_k||q_k) = \sum_k (p_k \cdot \log_2(p_k/q_k)),$$

364 where the minimum value is 0 when $p_k = q_k$. The theoretical maximum value occurs when p_k assigns all
 365 probability to a single soil type class (e.g. 1 for one class and 0 for others). In this case, the relative entropy
 366 will be $\log_2(N)$. For the soil types classification the theoretical maximum value is $\log_2(185) \approx 7.53$ units
 367 of information (bit). This measure helped identify regions where the model uncertainty was high, guiding
 368 areas for potential refinement.

369 RESULTS

370 Benchmarking of the models

371 Table 5 shows the cross-validation performance of the ML models with the dummy model. It is clear that
 372 both the LightGBM and RF models outperformed the dummy model that predicts the prior distribution of
 373 the classes. Log-loss ratios show the moderate decrease in the log-loss about 37%.

Table 5. Cross-validation performance of the benchmarked ML models to the dummy model. Abbreviations: EML— ensemble machine learning model, RF — Random forests.

Metrics	dummy	EML	LightGBM	RF
log loss (block CV, 110 soil types)	4.21	2.63	2.65	2.61
log loss ratio (block CV, 110 soil types)	NA	0.38	0.37	0.38
F1 score (block CV, 110 soil types)	0.01	0.23	0.24	0.21

374 Fig. 5 shows the 20 most important variables for the ML models combined into one diagram. We
 375 noticed some surprising differences here. The LightGBM model is mainly driven by the high resolution
 376 covariates of the relief (DTM) and the radar backscatter related to the soil factor. On the other hand, RF
 377 model is driven by the more coarse bio-climatic factor represented by the CHELSA layers. The models
 378 share 6 bio-climatic covariates in the top 10 related to isothermality and temperature seasonality (bio3
 379 and bio4), precipitation seasonality (bio15), surface downwelling shortwave radiation (rsds) and cloud
 380 area fraction (clt).

381 Fig. 6 shows the log loss ratios of LightGBM and RF models for the top 25% of the most frequent soil
 382 types. The log loss ratio is positive varying from 0.15 to 0.55 for both models, which indicates the higher
 383 performance compared to the dummy model. However, there is no significant evidence of superiority
 384 of one ML model over the other, which is also indicated in Fig. 5. The log-loss ratios reveals a slightly
 385 higher mean values for the LightGBM approximately in the 50% of the soil types. The other 50% shows
 386 the better performance of the RF when comparing the mean values. The interquantile range (IQR) of the
 387 boxplots overlaps in most cases.

388 Fig. 7 shows the differences in predictions of the LightGBM, RF and Ensemble models in the rural
 389 southern region of Czechia. We compare the spatial details of the predictions for the two selected soil
 390 types based on Fig. 6. The left panel shows the predicted probabilities of Haplic Chernozems. Haplic
 391 Chernozems reached the high log loss ratios (0.45-0.52) among the top 25% of the most frequent soil
 392 types despite the relatively low number of the training points. LightGBM predictions reveal higher
 393 spatial detail showing the individual fields to the RF predictions. The relatively higher performance of
 394 LightGBM is indicated by higher log loss ratios and non-overlapping IQR to the RF model. However,
 395 when comparing the predictions of Haplic Luvisols, the spatial detail of the predictions is similar. The

Figure 5. Feature importance of the ML models ordered ascending by the spatial resolution. Abbreviations: bio3 — isothermality, bio4 — temperature seasonality, bio6 — mean daily minimum air temperature of the coldest month, bio7 — annual range of air temperature, bio9 — mean daily mean air temperatures of the driest quarter, bio11 — mean daily mean air temperatures of the coldest quarter, bio12 — annual precipitation amount, bio15 — precipitation seasonality, bio16 — mean monthly precipitation amount of the wettest quarter, bio17 — mean monthly precipitation amount of the driest quarter, bio18 — mean monthly precipitation amount of the warmest quarter, bio19 — mean monthly precipitation amount of the coldest quarter, clt—cloud area fraction, cmi—climate moisture index, rsds—surface downwelling shortwave radiation, sfcWind—near-surface wind speed (Karger et al., 2017, 2021; Brun et al., 2022b,a)

396 classification performance of Haplic Luvisols is relatively low as indicated by log loss ratio (0.25-0.28)
 397 and the IQR overlap completely for the all three models. It indicates that the small differences in the
 398 mean log loss ratios are related to the ranking of the covariates, their different spatial resolution and their
 399 correlations to the individual soil types. Therefore, we decided to ensemble these two models into the
 400 final model for producing the maps when considering all the results in this subsection. Our results clearly
 401 show that the ensemble model is equally good as the individual models in the means of accuracy while it
 402 preserves the detailed spatial resolutions of the predictions coming from the DTM modified by the larger
 403 scale of the climate.

Figure 6. Log-loss ratios of the top 25% most frequent soil types in the training dataset in descending order by the number of the training points. The soil-type names are highlighted in the color of the ML model with higher mean value of the log loss ratio. LighGBM (LGB) is highlighted in blue. Random Forest is highlighted in orange. Ensemble of the LGB and RF is highlighted in green.

Figure 7. Spatial differences of the predicted probabilities of Haplic Chernozems (left panel) and Haplic Luvisols (right panel) in the rural region around Nové Mlýny reservoirs (48.898N, 16.650E) in southern Czechia. Nové Mlýny reservoirs are masked in the figure as all permanent water bodies in Europe. Google Maps (2022, CNES/Airbus, Maxar Technologies), available through <https://www.google.com/maps/>, last accessed: 20 September 2024.

404 **Predictions of the final model**

405 Table 6 shows the cross-validation performance of the final ML models to the dummy model. It is clear
 406 that both the LightGBM and RF models outperformed the dummy model. The log-loss ratios show the
 407 moderate decrease of the log-loss about 37% which is consistent with the results of the models classifying
 408 110 soil types in the Table 5. It indicates a solid generalization ability of the models and the robust
 409 predictive modeling workflow.

410 Fig. 8 compares the continental distribution of the predicted probabilities of the 4 most frequent soil
 411 types (Eutric and Dystric Cambisols, Haplic Luvisols and Albic Podzols) to the corresponding patterns
 412 in WRBFU map. The distribution of Cambisols matches well the WRBFU map, indicating the high

Table 6. Cross-validation performance of the final ML models to the dummy model

Metrics	dummy	EML	LightGBM	RF
log loss (stratified CV, 185 soil types)	4.41	2.76	2.76	2.76
log loss ratio (stratified CV, 185 soil types)	NA	0.37	0.37	0.37
F1 score (stratified CV, 185 soil types)	0.01	0.20	0.22	0.19

413 probability of Eutric Cambisols in highlands and mountainous regions in general. Dystric Cambisols
414 are present in the core parts of the major mountain ranges in Europe, especially in the Pyrenees, Alps,
415 Dynaric Alps, Balkan Mountains and Carpathians. The distribution of Albic Podzols matches the WRBFU
416 seems to also be predicted correctly. Likewise, the high probability of the Albic Podzols presence is in
417 Scandinavia, Denmark, highlands of the Baltic Sea region, Alps, Carpathians and other mountainous
418 regions of Central and Western Europe. The distribution of Haplic Luvisols follows the main pattern of
419 the WRBFU map showing the high probabilities in the plains of Europe (East European plain, Central
420 Europe, Pannonian lowlands, Belgium and France).

421 Fig. 9 compares spatial detail of our soil type predictions vs ESDB v2. The general pattern appears
422 to match, but our map shows a much higher spatial detail of the soil-type distribution, especially when
423 distinguishing Haplic Luvisols from Haplic Chernozems in the lowlands of the Vale and Eutric Fluvisols
424 and Eutric Gleysols in the floodplain. The spatial distribution of the soil types matches also better matches
425 with the distribution of the legacy SSS points due the higher spatial resolution. There are still some
426 mismatches, but the positive effect of spatial resolution is clear.

427 The new map also follows the Catena concept as is shown in Fig. 10 Eutric Fluvisols and Eutric
428 Gleysols appear in the the floodplain of Morava river formed by alluvial sediments. The rest of the
429 lowland which was transformed from the natural steppe to the agricultural region by human (Vovsova,
430 1962) is covered by Haplic Chernozems or Haplic Luvisols. The slopes of the Vale are covered by Dystric
431 Cambisols.

432 Fig. 11 shows the relative entropy map of the same area. The relative entropy varies from 2.37 to
433 5.52 which means an information gain to the dummy model having 0 relative entropy. The lowest values
434 are in for the floodplain covered by Gleysols and Fluvisols. The highest values are in area covered by
435 Luvisols. It can be interpreted as the probabilities of individual soil types close to each other in the areas
436 with lower relative entropy, i. e., there are more candidate soil types, compared to the areas with higher
437 values. In this case, our model is more uncertain of the soil type in the floodplain. There is a higher risk
438 of mismatching the most probable soil type in the area. However, the the ensemble model assigned the
439 correct soil type based on the maximum probability.

440 DISCUSSION

441 Summary findings

442 We have prepared a pan-EU compilation of training points with WRB soil classification and then overlaid
443 them versus cca. 130 covariate layers containing climatic variables (CHELSA Bioclimatic variables),
444 Landsat-based long-term (2000–2022) biophysical indices, multiscale terrain variables (at 30, 60, 120,

(a) WRB soil map from ESDB v2

(b) Dystric Cambisols

(c) Eutric Cambisols

(d) Albic (Haplic) Podzols

(e) Haplic Luvisols

Figure 8. Comparison of the predicted probabilities of the for most frequent soil types for pan-EU; pattern from the WRBFU map of ESDB v2. Abbreviations: ESDB v2 — European Soil Database v2 Raster Library at 1 km×1 km resolution (Panagos et al., 2022).

445 240, 480 and 960 m resolutions) and parent material variables. Benchmarking of LightGBM and RF
 446 based models revealed the comparable accuracy represented by the log loss and log los ratio scores (see
 447 Table 6). However, further analysis of the variable importance showed that the LightGBM model is driven

Figure 9. A detailed predictions of the EML model overlaid by legacy SSS soil profiles (Žižala et al., 2022) compared to the WRBFU map from European Soil Database v2 Raster Library 1kmx1km (Panagos et al., 2022) in the Hornomoravsky Uval (Vale of Upper Morava River) south to Olomouc city (49.594N, 17.251E), Czechia. Google Maps (2022, CNES/Airbus, Maxar Technologies), available through <https://www.google.com/maps/>, last accessed: 20 September 2024.

448 by high-resolution relief and soil covariates and the RF model was driven by coarse-resolution bioclimatic
 449 features. It affected the spatial detail of the predicted probabilities and the log loss scores of the top 25% of
 450 the most frequent soil types in the training dataset (see Fig. 6 and Fig. 7). Therefore, we have fitted models
 451 to predict 185 targeted soil types by ensembling two models i.e. averaging the probabilities of the Light
 452 GBM and RF models. The accuracy assessment of the final model indicates a moderate improvement of
 453 the log loss scores about 37% to the dummy model. Visually, the produced predictions match existing
 454 coarse resolution (1 km) pan-EU products, but then reveal significantly more detail, especially in areas
 455 with complex topography. In comparison to our previous global predictions at a much coarser resolution
 456 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7820796>) this is certainly a major improvement considering
 457 the level of detail, computing optimization, and usability. Overall, this framework produced estimates of
 458 main WRB soil types for Europe at very high spatial resolution, and hence can be used at farm scale.

459 **Advantages and limitations**

460 The main advantages of the maps and the mapping system we have used include:

- 461 • **30 m resolution allows for farm-scale decisions:** The high spatial resolution of predictions allows
 462 for farm-scale assessment i.e. it matches in resolution most detailed data sets produced by the
 463 European Environmental Agency and the Copernicus Land Monitoring Program. The similar

Figure 10. Example of a 3D representation of the landscape from Fig. 9 (hard classes) with drainage lines overlaid on the top. This illustrate that at 30 m spatial resolution, the soil-catenas are consistent and mezo-relief is well-represented.

464 spatial resolution lower than 50 m was considered sufficient for farm-scale decision in the previous
 465 national studies (Chen et al., 2023; Pásztor et al., 2018). Žižala et al. (2022) produced maps in 20
 466 m spatial resolution, but the authors discussed the low ratio computing costs/benefits for farmers.
 467 Stoorvogel et al. (2015) recommended the spatial around 30 m to be consistent with the operational
 468 stripe width of the heavy agrotechnics.

- 469 • **EO-soilmapper is a fully automated system:** generating predictions is relatively inexpensive,
 470 which means that we can quickly update maps as soon countries, departments, research groups
 471 donate more points.
- 472 • **EO-soilmapper includes multi-scale data:** We also use as covariates multi-scale DTM variables,
 473 monthly and annual values of climatic variables so that overall we think we represent the scale
 474 factor. citace. The multi-scale approach reveals spatial relief structures at different scales, leading
 475 to an increase in prediction accuracy in digital soil mapping (Behrens et al., 2010; Cavazzi et al.,
 476 2013; Behrens et al., 2018).

477 We are aware (and do not hide) that the overlap in the probabilities produced, i.e. confusion between

Figure 11. Example of relative entropy compared to the maximally uncertain scenario (Kullback-Leibler divergence — lower values indicate higher uncertainty) for the study area shown in Fig. 9. Google Maps (2022, CNES/Airbus, Maxar Technologies), available through <https://www.google.com/maps/>, last accessed: 20 September 2024.

478 the classes, is often high, with an effective increase in accuracy of 37% for the random dummy model, but
 479 showing a relatively low F1 score (20%). We believe that the key reasons for the limited accuracy we
 480 observed can be grouped into the following four themes:

- 481 • **Soil polypedons are in general hidden, fuzzy objects and transitions between two polypedons**
 482 **are complex:** Predicting probabilities of the soil types showed beneficial to map polypedons
 483 compared to their hard class equivalent, especially when the predictions were far from the observa-
 484 tion points (Lagacherie and Voltz, 2000; Jafari et al., 2012). We have never expected to produce
 485 hard-class map of soil types where the average mapping accuracy is >90% which is the case e.g.
 486 in land cover mapping or forest-type mapping where all objects are above ground (Witjes et al.,
 487 2022). The resulting log-loss ratios are comparable to the regional study of (Ließ et al., 2011).
 488 Therefore we consider as the major improvement of the study reaching comparable accuracy, but at
 489 the continental scale. We also calculated per-pixel relative entropy to inform the users about the
 490 uncertainty. The relative entropy is rather the indication of the areas with complex soil polypedons
 491 resulting in predicting very close probabilities of more than two soil types, or the areas where the
 492 training points are sparse or missing. Therefore the relative entropy map can be used to identify the
 493 areas where additional sampling is needed to increase the accuracy of the predictions, i.e. applying
 494 two-stage sampling (Zhang et al., 2016; Szatmári et al., 2019).
- 495 • **Variable quality of training points and noise introduced as an effect of difference between**
 496 **different WRB versions:** The training points we have used to build pan-EU models are far from
 497 ideal as these are not based on probability sampling and the soil classification (WRB) has gone

498 through 3–4 adaptations. Almost 60% of points used in this paper are no original WRB designations
499 but are only our attempt to harmonize data and bring all observations to one legend. Also note that
500 for many data sets we could not even find enough metadata to be able to judge on which soil type
501 reference system.

502 • **Large geographical gaps / inconsistent density of training points:** Even though we have tried
503 inserting some pseudo-observations to help decrease variable representation of various climatic and
504 landscape zones, it is obvious from the Fig. 3 that density of training points is highly inconsistent.
505 Unfortunately determination of soil types was not of interest to LUCAS soil survey and hence we
506 can only work with national / project data sets.

507 • **Soil types are results of past long-term processes, models are based on current covariates :**
508 Soil types we experience now on landscapes have formed in the past +10k years (Eckmeier et al.,
509 2007; Velichko and Morozova, 2010), but we use current climatic maps to model their distribution.
510 This is not ideal and hence what we predict and what we observe in the field will differ.

511 Our choice of 185 classes can be considered arbitrary, and this is a known problem: Bouma et al. (2022)
512 “*what is the most effective level of the soil classification system to be considered?*” In our framework,
513 the preferred approach is to model the distribution of soil types at the lowest level, then to aggregate
514 probabilities. We had to set a threshold for the level of detail in the WRB for purely practical reasons,
515 as otherwise the number of classes with too few observations can become significant. The modeling
516 framework can still be improved; however, some choices such as number of classes and assignment of
517 quality flags will remain subjective; or at least we do not see a solution to this problem yet.

518 We also believe that the world needs a more robust Universal Soil Classification system that can be
519 used across borders and that does not make all existing observations of soil types obsolete.

520 **Potential future development directions**

521 One of the bottlenecks of producing high quality soil type maps for Europe is the scarcity of training
522 points. Compared to the USA, where almost half million points with a detailed soil classification are
523 available in the National Soil Information System (Ramcharan et al., 2018), Europe seems to have on
524 the order of magnitude less resources for quality soil type mapping using Machine Learning. We believe
525 that the field of soil classification could benefit a lot from AI-based systems that help directly classify
526 soil profiles from photographs and/or soil spectroscopy scans. Gyasi and Purushotham (2023) provides a
527 review of the deep learning techniques that are used to directly determine soil types using photographs
528 (and there must be hundreds of thousands of photographs of soil profiles even in the public domain,
529 e.g. <https://www.flickr.com/photos/jakelley/>) that could help generate more training points.
530 Some countries, such as Mexico, are now publishing their national data sets with geoharmonized field
531 photographs of soil profiles (Gallegos and Bautista, 2022). In Scotland, colleagues at the Hutton Institute
532 have developed an app that runs on a mobile phone and is able to predict soil properties and soil types just
533 based on a photograph, e.g. from a mini-pit (Aitkenhead et al., 2016).

534 Another interesting development direction for this work is to try adding even more covariate layers
535 that represent key soil forming factors, e.g. ground-water depth variables (monthly), even some soil

536 properties such as depth to bedrock and similar. It is possible that the mapping accuracy can still be
537 improved with more relevant data, although this would require a number of smaller mapping projects
538 in-itself. In addition, in this work we did not consider that soil types change over time. They do, of course,
539 but would 20 years of data be enough to observe changes in soil types at at least 10% of pixels?

540 **Recommended uses of the soil type predictions**

541 The intended uses of the 30 m resolution maps include, but are not limited to:

- 542 1. to help distinguish different soil regions (cross between soil types and climatic variables),
- 543 2. to assist in predictive soil mapping of soil properties with limited laboratory data,
- 544 3. to serve as a covariate in agronomy and forestry models, e.g. to map yields and for species
545 distribution mapping.

546 We especially support the use of these maps to produce soil regions, that is the most homogeneous
547 landscape units where soils and (meso-)climate are relatively constant. For this, we recommend using
548 objective unsupervised clustering techniques, so that the output regions are as objective as possible and
549 cannot be manipulated. As inputs for deriving soil regions, one can use all probabilities and key climatic
550 variables e.g. monthly min, average and max temperature and monthly precipitation, then optimize the
551 number of soil regions (possibly a few thousands) and their distribution. This will come with a number of
552 challenges, for example, helping downscale climatic variables to 30 m (usually only available at resolutions
553 1–5 km) and also unsupervised clustering at such large raster objects could become computationally
554 demanding.

555 **CONCLUSIONS**

556 We have produced next-generation high-resolution predictions of 185 soil types based on the WRB
557 classification for Europe for the reference period 2000–2022. The predictions of 2D soil-type probabilities
558 (0–100%) and soil type (hard classes) are part of the Soil Health Data cube for Europe ([https://shdc.
559 ai4soilhealth.eu](https://shdc.ai4soilhealth.eu)), which is one of the main deliverables of the AI4SoilHealth project (an open access
560 European-wide digital infrastructure for monitoring and forecasting soil health indicators). The use of
561 probabilities is more in line with the natural overlap of soil types thematically and geographically (Rossiter
562 et al., 2022). The produced 30 m WRB soil types dataset produced can be used for both direct analysis,
563 stratification, and formation of soil districts, in the context of the European Soil Health law EU legislation
564 (Panagos et al., 2024), and as valuable inputs for crop-yield modeling, land use management planning.

565 Producing these predictions is relatively inexpensive (compared to, e.g. Tian et al. (2024b)), and the
566 predictions can be updated daily. We are keen to update and improve these predictions provided that soil
567 and agronomy research organizations share their legacy soil data with us so that we can rerun models and
568 gradually produce more and more accurate map of soil types.

569 The world probably needs an Universal Soil Classification (USC) system that will be compatible
570 with most existing taxonomy systems and that is open, regularly maintained, and that matches similar
571 taxonomy systems as species in biology, ecosystem types and land cover types in ecology, climate types
572 in climate science, and similar (Hughes, 2017; Nikiforova and Fleis, 2018).

573 The data and code used are publicly available under an open license from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838408> and <https://github.com/AI4SoilHealth/>.
574

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583 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

584 The author(s) declares that they have no competing interests. Robert Minarik, Tomislav Hengl, Rolf
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